

**TO STUDY THE PERFORMANCE OF BODIES IN
REPRODUCTION OF THE HERD***Berdiyev Maksed -student**Yusupov Dilshod - student**Tlevbaeva Zaynab-assistant**Mamatov Xurshid Abdirafievich.k.x.f.d(PhD).**Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine University of Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology,
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Abstract. The article provides data on the reproductive ability of heifers inseminated at different levels of live body weight. Heifers with normal growth and development had high rates of reproduction, which contributed to early replenishment of the cattle herd with highly productive cows.

Keywords. Holstein breed, body, heifer, cow, growth, development, feed, storage conditions, herd reproduction, insemination index, breeding farm.

Introduction. Herd reproduction is the most urgent problem in cattle breeding, and the fate of the industry depends on its solution.

To milk cows and get calves from them, to raise the obtained calves and produce meat, the cow must become a calf and give birth. This is a complex and responsible event because it is closely related to biological and organizational factors.

Effective use of one head of a cow in a year is a zootechnical concept, in which it is understood that one head of a calf and 300-305 days of milking from a cow every year. For this, it is necessary to correctly organize the physiological cycles of cows throughout the year. That's why, on the farm, calculations are carried out for each cow and heifer. As a result of not knowing the physiological conditions of cows, there are cases of them remaining barren.

Farms should achieve 85 calves per 100 cows per year. Unfortunately, the number of farms achieving such a result is small.

Getting one calf per year from each cow is considered one of the main tasks in such herds, and one of the important tasks of selection work. Because of this, it is of great practical importance to inseminate cows after they have given birth [3; pp. 30-31].

[2; pp. 25-27] Studies showed that keeping cows reared under high feeding conditions and calving for the first time at 24 months of age and later calving under conditions of full value

feeding allowed them to produce record cows and the lifetime milk yield of cows calving at such an early age for the first time it was observed that it was 18-20% higher than that of cows that gave birth at a late age, and a large number of calves were obtained from them.

According to [1; pp. 15-16], determining and using optimal periods of insemination of cows after giving birth is an important factor in increasing the volume of milk production, increasing the number of cattle, and increasing the efficiency of the industry.

The purpose of the study. Study herd reproduction indicators of Holstein breed bodies, and get acquainted with innovative technologies used in the production of dairy products at the farm.

Research object and methods. Holstein bodies of Danish selection. All information about carcasses was obtained from the pedigree animal certificate. Bodies weighing 330 kg were attached to the first group, and 360 kg to the second group. Herd reproduction indicators of bodies were studied by methods generally accepted in zootechnics.

Research results and analysis.

In our research, we first got acquainted with the innovative technologies used in the production of dairy products at the farm. All heavy work on the farm is mechanized and automated. Feed is ground, mixed, and transferred to a large hopper in the STARMAKS equipment. Feeds are distributed to cows twice a day through a large mixer hopper of a Belarusian tractor. For irrigation, 250 l troughs are installed in the pastures, and when the water is full, the water is automatically stopped. Milking of cows In the state of Israel, a computerized system for 16 cows "Milking hall" manufactured by AFIMILK company has been installed. During the milking of cows, the amount of milk, electrical conductivity, and AFILAB equipment determines the amount of fat, protein, lactose, number of somatic cells, and urea in milk. The RESPONDER equipment installed on the legs of the cows detects the number of steps, rest time, and state of the cow. In addition, the cow herd management program is installed in the milking hall, in which the data such as the milking of the cows, the time of leaving the milk, and the time of giving birth are recorded on the computer, as well as the information about the procedures performed by the veterinarians on the cows. transferred, it is divided into liquid and dry states. Dry manure can be used as a fertilizer. The liquid part is sent as organic fertilizer to the fields where food is grown. It can be concluded that all processes in milk production on the farm are based on modern technologies.

Growing a live weight of 330-380 kg at the standard age of 12-17 months through rapid body growth is an important zootechnical activity, responsibility, and hard work. The

characteristics of the herd regeneration of bodies are controlled by feeding and storage conditions, the norm.

The Holstein breed is distinguished from many breeds by its quickness. In advanced foreign countries, the bodies of the herd are being fertilized even from the age of 12 months. At this time, their live weight is 310-330 kg.

In our research, we studied the herd reproduction performance of Holsteins. The farm has all the conditions for growing and keeping bodies. The bodies were fed on the same type of feeding ration. Their storage was carried out on the porch. In winter, the porches are covered with polyethylene. Our studies have shown that sexual maturation of bodies, awakening of sexual reflexes, and first sexual cycles are observed from 9-10 months. Physiologically, it happened at 14 months, and it was observed that at this time their live weight was 330-360 kg. In the experiment, two groups of carcasses were formed at the age of 14 months (421-420 days) with a live weight of 330 kg and 360 kg. Burnt bodies were removed from the herd in the morning and evening in groups. The bodies were artificially inseminated twice in the morning and the evening with an interval of 12 hours.

Table 1

Indicators of herd reproduction of bodies, $X \pm S_x$

(n-10)

Indicators	Groups	
	I	II
Live weight at birth, kg	505±4,3	552±5,5
Age at insemination, days	421±3,0	420±2,0
Live weight during spawning, kg	330,3±2,21	360,5±2,42
Fertilization index, times	2,1±0,22	2,0±0,11
Fertilized from first insemination, %	60,0	65,0
Duration of straitness, days	284,8±0,65	282,5±1,05
Age at first birth, days	705,8±1,85	702,5±2,25

The data in Table 1 shows that bodies with accelerated growth and development were 30.3 kg ahead of their peers in terms of live weight. The difference in the age of fertilization of bodies between groups was one day. At the time of calving, the heifers of the second group were 47 kg superior to their peers in the first group. So they are developed in activity. The fertility rate from the first insemination was higher in the second group, i.e. 5% higher. Although the duration of the strait period is 2-3 days in the bodies of the first group, it can be called normal.

Summary. Although the age of some carcasses in the herd was the same, it was observed that the live weight was slightly lower depending on the individual characteristics, but this did not negatively affect the performance of the reproduction of the herd. In both groups, herd reproduction rates were normal. Due to proper feeding and storage of carcasses on the farm, it is possible to form a herd of productive cows earlier.

Used literature

1. Казеев Г.В. Оптимальные сроки осеменения коров.//“Зоотехния”. Москва, 2005, №10, с. 22-28.
2. Сергеев И.И. Целесообразность раннего оплодотворения телок. // “Зоотехния”. Москва, 2005, № 4, с. 25-27.
3. Чекушкин А.М. Возрастная структура стада и воспроизводительные способности коров различных родственных групп в племенных хозяйствах Московской области. // “Зоотехния”. Москва, 2011, №4, с. 30-31.